

FATIGUE DAMAGE IN NICALON SiC(f)/AL COMPOSITE WIRES

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SUMMARY: To understand the fatigue damage mechanism in Nicalon SiC(f)/Al composite, the wires of SiC(f)/Al were fabricated by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method. Tensile -- tensile fatigue test on the composite wires was carried out at stress ratio $R=0.1$ at room temperature and at 573 K . Tests show that the dominant damage model in the wire is progressive fiber fracture and the progressive fiber fracture is due to the deorientation of fiber to the stress axis. Test at 573 K shows no evident differences in the fatigue property between room temperature and 573 K . The wires after exposure at 873 K for 30 minutes, through the interface bonding force has been increased by interface reaction, are of lower fatigue property than those unexposed.

KEY WORDS: metal-matrix composite, silicon carbide fiber, fatigue damage

INTRODUCTION

Despite its evident importance in numerous engineering application, few published investigation exist on the fatigue properties and damage of SiC multifilaments reinforced Aluminum composite. The specimens used in this paper are composite wires with the fibers uniaxially oriented in the loading direction. Its fatigue failure mode is different from the fatigue crack growth mode in short fibers reinforced aluminum composite[1]. The fatigue failure mode in continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC) is controlled by the following three constituents of the system: fiber, matrix, and fiber/matrix interface. W.S.Jonson basing on the relative strain to fatigue failure grouped possible failure modes of MMC into three categories[2]--- matrix dominated, fiber dominated and self-similar damage growth. The purpose of this paper is to find the failure mode and damage process in this composite wires. The experiment results also provide a method to improve the fatigue properties of SiC fiber/Al composite.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS & METHODS

The composite wire used here is reinforced by a bind of 500 Nicalon SiC fibers produced by NIPPON Carbon Co. Ltd. The matrix is industrial pure Al 1100 infiltrated by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method. Total wire length of a batch is 200 to 500 meters and the fibers are oriented in the length direction. Specimen cut from the same batch of wire are 50 mm and have the same mechanical properties. The main properties of the fiber and composite wire are listed in table 1. Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted in load control on a $1 \times 10^3\text{N}$

EHF FB01-4LA material test machine with a stress ratio $R=0.1$. A sinusoidal waveform with a frequency of 20 Hz was used. The fatigue fractograph is observed by a S-360 scanning electron microscope.

Table 1: The main properties of the fiber and composite wire

materials	diameter	density (g/cm^3)	UTS (MPa)	E (GPa)	V_f %
SiC_f	10-15 μm	2.55	2500-3000	180-200	-
wire	0.52 mm	2.60	1100-1200	110-120	40-45

Load/elongation curve was detected by a punctuation extensometer and recorded by means of an X-Y recorder. If the specimens fractured near the grips its date would not be count in. Specimens tested at 573 K were heated by a tube stove and the gips were not in the stove.

Fig. 1: S-N curve of NICALON SiC_f/Al composite wire

□ ---- at room temperature
• ---- at 573 K

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 is the S--N curve of the composite wires. From the curve it can be known that the fatigue stress to failure is decreased quickly with the increase of cycle numbers. When the cycle index is 10^6 its fatigue strength is 440 MPa, less than one half of its static tensile strength. For fibers in the wire is ceramic material and its fatigue stress to failure generally has no relationship with the numbers of stress cycle. The fatigue strength of the Al matrix is more than 90% of its static tension stress while the fatigue cycle number is 10^6 [3]. Why does the fatigue stress of the composite wire decrease so rapidly?

To find the reason, a fatigue test at 573 K was taken on the wires. At this temperature the mechanical properties of fiber can not be influenced, but the properties of Al matrix can be changed. Test result is shown in fig. 1. The composite wire at 573 K is of the same fatigue property with its room temperature. Treated the wire at 873 K for 30 min. than test its fatigue property at $S_{\text{max}}=700$ MPa at room temperature. The cycle index to failue is 5×10^2 — 5×10^3 and much lower than that of untreated specimen. Nicalon SiC fibers can react with Al at 873--913 K and form Al_2O_3 and Al_4C_3 . This interface reaction can increase the bonding force between fibers and matrix and can decrease the mechanical properties of the fibers in the

specimens. So the fatigue damage in this composite wire must be mainly dominated by the fibers.

Fig. 2: The relation of static tensile strength with fatigue cycle number
 x---- $S_{max}=700$ MPa o ---- $S_{max}=450$ MPa

Fig. 3: The photomicrograph of the composite wire $\times 100$

Fig 4: The SEM fatigue fractograph of the composite wire

To find the fatigue damage process in the wire, a specimen after 10^6 cycles on $S_{max}=450$ MPa and a specimen fractured by static tensile test have been extracted by NaOH solution. The two specimens are of the same length (50 mm) before extracted. The fiber in the fatigue specimen become short about 5 mm, but the fiber in static test specimen is about 50 mm same with the length of fibers in untested specimen. To confirm this fiber fracture process during fatigue test, several specimens stressed on $S_{max}=700$ MPa and $S_{max}=450$ MPa were tested to different cycle

numbers and then tested their static tensile strength. The relation between cycle numbers and static tensile strength are shown in Fig. 2. The tensile strength is decline with the increase of fatigue cycle index. So the fibers fracture must be progressive as the fatigue test going. This fiber length after fatigue test at certain conditions can also give us some information about the bonding force between fiber and matrix.

What made the fibers in fatigue specimen fractured one by one? For the composite wire was fabricated by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method and exists the deorientation in the length direction, as shown in photomicrograph (Fig. 3). The deorientation resulted in the stress difference among the fibers during fatigue test. The Al matrix displayed a good special fatigue ductility and cooperated with the rotation of fibers while one fiber of hard orientation fractured after another. A SEM fatigue fractograph as Fig. 4 shows that the Al matrix in a specimen after 10^6 cycles is still appeared as a ductility fractograph characteristic. Electric conductivity of the fatigue specimen before and after fatigue test is unchanged too. The specimen elongation during the fatigue process was detected and the result is shown on Fig. 5. This specimen elongation may be caused by improving its fiber deorientation and that is the reason of the fiber fractured one by one.

Fig. 5: The specimen elongation during the fatigue test

CONCLUSION

1. The progressive fiber fracture is the dominant damage model in this composite wire.
2. The deorientation of the fibers to the stress axis resulted in the fibers fracture one by one and this fatigue process is with the cooperation of matrix fatigue ductility.

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REFERENCES

1. Xi Cong Liu and C. Bathias, "Fatigue damage development in Al₂O₃/Al composite", Composites, Vol.24, No. 3(1993)pp282-287
2. W.S.Johnson, "Fatigue damage accumulation in various metal matrix composites", NASA Technical Memorandum 89116, N87-18416, 1987
3. G.J.Dvorak and W.S.Johnson, International Journal of Fracture 16(1980)585-607